

Simplified Self-Coherent FSO Transmission Boosted by Digital Resolution Enhancer

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Abstract—The joint application of free-space optics (FSO) transmission with coherent detection has recently been shown to enable unprecedented optical wireless capacity. Nevertheless, due to the associated cost and power consumption, simplified self-coherent FSO links are currently being explored to optimize the performance vs. complexity tradeoff. In particular, the utilization of low-complexity virtual carrier self-coherent transmission provides an appealing cost-effective alternative for high-capacity FSO links. However, this transmission paradigm is associated with quantization noise problems due to limited digital-to-analog converter (DAC) resolution. Following all the stated requirements, this work presents a simplified virtual carrier-assisted self-coherent FSO link supported by a low-resolution DAC and Nyquist rate phase reconstruction using the DC-Value algorithm. The utilization of such a low-resolution DAC is aided by a digital resolution enhancement (DRE) method. Employing this simplified self-coherent approach, we experimentally demonstrated 100 Gbps FSO transmission over an outdoor 42 m link using a DAC with resolution as low as 3 bits.

Index Terms—self-coherent, virtual carrier, quantization noise, digital resolution enhancer, free space optics.

I. INTRODUCTION

OPTICAL wireless communications, also known as free space optics (FSO), have been extensively investigated over the last few decades as a potential solution to address the ever-increasing bandwidth and capacity requirements [1], [2]. In this regard, the use of coherent communications, together with FSO, has recently been found in various applications, ranging from short-reach intra/inter-data center networks [3] to long-reach applications, such as inter-satellite [4] and satellite-to-earth communications [5]. Consequently, some record FSO transmission demonstrations have also been performed, with the capacity of per-channel bit-rates spanning from 400 Gbps [6] up to 1 Tbps [7], [8].

Despite the massive capacity and potential demonstrated by these fully-coherent FSO systems, their practical applicability

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might be restrained due to their high-cost and power consumption. Therefore, to address the aforementioned challenges, several reduced-complexity quasi-coherent approaches have been proposed to optimize the balance between hardware complexity and achievable bit-rate. Following this need, we have recently demonstrated a self-coherent FSO transmission using a Kramers-Kronig (KK) receiver [9], which permits the use of a single photodiode and analog-to-digital converter (ADC), per polarization, while still being compatible with phase-preserving receiver-side post-processing and employment of advanced modulation formats [10]. Notice that, such simplified coherent FSO architecture has attracted significant attention, being the subject of several recent studies on achievable capacity [11], [12]. Despite the considerable complexity reduction enabled by the KK-based self-coherent FSO (KK-FSO) system, there are still some challenges to overcome in terms of cost and power consumption. For instance, the requirement of a carrier tone sitting at the edge of the information spectrum is mandatory to alleviate the effects of signal-to-signal beating noise (SSBN) [13]–[15]. The required carrier tone can be added either in the radio frequency (RF) domain [16], optical domain [14], or digital domain [17]. Notice that both RF and optical methods increase hardware requirements and complexity, making the insertion of the virtual carrier in the digital domain a simple alternative to get rid of these extra resource requirements [17]. Nevertheless, the virtual carrier increases the signal’s dynamic range [18], which consequently incurs a quantization noise penalty due to the finite resolution of the DAC.

Recently, a digital resolution enhancer (DRE) method was proposed to alleviate the effects of quantization noise of low-resolution DACs [19], [20]. Unlike conventional rounding-off (RO) quantizers, the DRE utilizes the dynamic quantization (DQ) approach that can effectively reduce the in-band quantization noise and improve the transmission performance [19], [20]. Exploring this DRE method, we propose a novel self-coherent FSO system that further simplifies our previous KK-FSO work [9]. On the transmitter side, we replace the optical carrier with a virtual carrier [21]. The virtual carrier is added directly to the signal in the digital domain, avoiding additional hardware to generate and lock the optical carrier with the signal. Furthermore, the DRE method [19] is applied to enable the use of very low-resolution DACs with only 3 physical number of bits (PNOBs), significantly reducing cost and power consumption. Finally, on the receiver side, we replace the KK transform with our recently proposed DC-Value method [17]. This improves power efficiency by reducing both oversampling

and carrier-to-signal power ratio (CSPR) requirements.

This article presents the full-length extension of our work presented at OFC 2023 [22], providing an in-depth analysis of the limitations of clipping with the virtual carrier. Also, it presents a detailed explanation of the application of DRE that addresses the quantization noise limitations, together with additional experimental results. Apart from the introduction, this paper comprises four sections. In Section II, we describe the limitations of adding a virtual carrier to the self-coherent system. In Section III, we present the DRE and quantization noise analysis. Section IV presents the obtained experimental results over a 42 m FSO link for the DRE-enhanced self-coherent detection. Finally, in the last section, we present the major concluding remarks.

II. LIMITATIONS OF DAC IN VIRTUAL CARRIER SELF-COHERENT SYSTEMS

In this section, we explore and numerically assess the challenges and performance impact associated with the use of a limitation of employing virtual carrier in self-coherent systems. To enable the phase retrieval process at the receiver, the virtual carrier power must be kept sufficiently high to satisfy the required minimum phase condition upon square-law detection [13]. This requirement gives rise to the CSPR parameter, given as,

$$\text{CSPR} = \frac{P_{\text{carrier}}}{P_{\text{signal}}} \quad (1)$$

where P_{carrier} and P_{signal} represent the power of the carrier and signal, respectively. The CSPR value is usually kept such that it satisfies $P_{\text{carrier}} \geq P_{\text{signal,max}}$, where P_{carrier} and $P_{\text{signal,max}}$ represent the carrier power and peak signal power, respectively.

In self-coherent systems, the employment of the virtual carrier relaxes the additional hardware requirement as schematically shown in Fig. 1. Nevertheless, the insertion of such a high-power digital carrier tone expands the signal's dynamic range, (see Fig. 2), consequently increasing the quantization noise. The analysis shown in Fig. 2 presents the histogram of the in-phase signal component before (Fig. 2a) and after (Fig. 2b) insertion of the virtual carrier. Fig. 2a shows that the signal without the virtual carrier exhibits around $\sim 600 \text{ mV}_{\text{pp}}$ amplitude, where mV_{pp} represents peak-to-peak amplitude in millivolts. After insertion of the virtual carrier, see Fig. 2b, the value of peak-to-peak amplitude increases to $\sim 1600 \text{ mV}_{\text{pp}}$. This expanded voltage dynamic range increases the rounding-off quantization step-size, Δ , during the quantization process, consequently translating into a higher quantization noise power (as the variance of quantization noise is proportional to $\Delta^2/12$ [18]).

A. Signal Clipping

The reduction in quantization step size, Δ , can be attained by digital signal clipping. The introduction of clipping helps reduce the dynamic range of the signal, which consequently translates into the reduction of DAC quantization noise. However, it should be noted that signal clipping also introduces

Fig. 1: Insertion of the virtual carrier in the digital domain to enable phase recovery in minimum phase signal based self-coherent transceivers.

Fig. 2: Histogram of the signal (a) after pulse shaping, (b) after virtual carrier insertion.

clipping noise. The amplitude of the clipping noise is given as [18],

$$c(i) = \begin{cases} \text{sign}(s(i)) \left(K - \frac{\Delta}{2} \right) - s(i) & \text{if } |s(i)| > K \\ 0 & \text{if } |s(i)| \leq K \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $s(i)$ represents the i^{th} sample of information signal, $K = (2^{N_b} \Delta)/2$ is the clipping threshold, with N_b representing the number of bits. The variance of the clipping noise σ_c^2 can be extracted before quantization and the signal-to-clipping noise ratio (SCNR) can be calculated as,

$$\text{SCNR} = \sigma^2 / \sigma_c^2 \quad (3)$$

where σ^2 is the variance of the signal. The signal to quantization noise ratio (SQNR) can be improved at the expense of degrading the SCNR. Nevertheless, the performance of the DAC due to the clipping and quantization noise can be written as [18],

$$\text{SNR}_{\text{DAC}} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\text{SQNR}} + \frac{1}{\text{SCNR}}} \quad (4)$$

Note that the validity of (4) requires the clipping distortion to be uncorrelated with both signal and quantization noise. However, (2) suggests that clipping noise is correlated with the signal. Nevertheless, for clipping values that optimize the SNR_{DAC} , the assumption of uncorrelated holds valid [18].

B. Clipping in virtual carrier assisted self-coherent system

In virtual carrier self-coherent systems, clipping can be applied either to the (i) virtual carrier only, (ii) information signal only, or (iii) virtual carrier added information signal.

Fig. 3: Simulation model used to assess the impact of the clipping in self-coherent detection.

Fig. 4: Obtained optimum GMI vs. CSPP. Clipping values are optimized based on (4).

Fig. 5: Limitations of a virtual carrier in the self-coherent detection.

Fig. 3 presents the simulation model used for the clipping performance analysis. In the simulation, a 30 Gbaud PCS-36QAM signal with a net 100 Gbps bit-rate was used for the performance assessment. In Fig. 4, it is shown the obtained generalized mutual information (GMI) [23] as a function of CSPP for the aforementioned clipping strategies. The obtained GMI performance shown in Fig. 4 corresponds to the optimum clipping level for the given CSPP values. The optimum clipping values are adjusted based on (4), which provides maximum SNR_{DAC} . Results show that the application of clipping on the virtual carrier added information signal provides better performance among the previously mentioned three possible configurations. Following that, in this work, we apply clipping on the virtual carrier-added information signal throughout our analysis. It should be noted that when we refer to the optical carrier-assisted self-coherent system, the clipping is only applied to the information signal.

C. Optical vs virtual carrier assisted self-coherent system

This subsection presents a comparative performance analysis of the optical vs. virtual carrier-assisted self-coherent

transceivers. For the optical carrier self-coherent transceiver, a continuous wave (CW) tone is added at the transmitter end from the same laser source used for the modulation. Here, we similarly employ a 30 Gbaud PCS-36QAM signal with a net 100 Gbps bit-rate for the performance assessment. Fig. 5 presents the obtained GMI at an optimum CSPP for both optical and virtual carrier self-coherent as a function of PNOBs. Without clipping, results show that virtual carrier self-coherent incurs ~ 0.38 GMI penalty compared to optical carrier self-coherent transceiver at 4 PNOBs. Further, when clipping is employed in the virtual carrier self-coherent system, it results in a 0.1 GMI gain. Nevertheless, still there exists a significant performance gap of ~ 0.28 GMI between virtual and optical carrier self-coherent transceivers. Besides that, at 3 PNOBs, the performance gap increases to ~ 1.12 GMI. Further, we performed analysis for other high-order modulation constellations, such as PCS-64QAM, and found similar penalty trends. Results shown in Fig. 5 indicate that it requires > 5 PNOBs to alleviate the effects of virtual carrier dominant quantization noise.

III. DRE AND QUANTIZATION NOISE ANALYSIS

This section presents combined clipping and a DRE-employed virtual carrier self-coherent transceiver, which effectively reduces the overall DAC noise.

A. DRE and Notations

In this subsection, we briefly cover the system model used for the implementation of the DRE in a virtual carrier self-coherent transceiver. At the transmitter end (see Fig. 6), the transmitter digital signal processing (TX-DSP) generates a virtual carrier-added information signal $x(n)$ which is then dynamically quantized by the DRE to $x_q(n)$. For the case of the DRE, the dynamic quantization noise for each sample, $q_{dq}(n)$, can be given as [19],

$$q_{dq}(n) = x_q(n) - x(n) \quad (5)$$

which can be rewritten as,

$$q_{dq}(n) = q_{ro}(n) + u(n)\Delta \quad (6)$$

where $q_{ro}(n)$ is the rounding-off quantization noise without the employment of the DRE, Δ is the quantization step size, and $u(n)$ is an integer control sequence whose value can be chosen from [19], [20],

$$-\left(\frac{M-1}{2}\right) : 1 : \left(\frac{M+1}{2}\right) \quad (7)$$

where M is an odd integer number, and $:$ is an incremental operator. The value of M should be chosen in a manner such that it satisfies the $c_{min} \leq q_{ro} + u(n)\Delta \leq c_{max}$, where c_{min}

Fig. 6: Simulation model used to implement the DRE. At the transmitter side, a root-raised cosine (RRC) pulse shaping generates $x(n)$ which is then dynamically quantized by DRE to $x_q(n)$. At the receiver end, self-coherent detection is employed and followed by a matched filter which outputs the signal denoted by $y_q(n)$.

Fig. 7: Analysis of the quantization with (w/) and without (w/o) DRE with PNOBs = 4. (a) RO quantization noise q_{ro} w/o DRE, (b) DQ noise q_{dq} w/ DRE, (c) effective quantization noise q_{eff} w/o DRE, (d) effective quantization noise q_{eff} w/ DRE. The implementation of DRE effectively reduces the harmonics that arise from the RO quantization of the virtual carrier. (The DRE is implemented with $L = 3$ & $M = 3$)

and c_{max} are the minimum and maximum quantizer output values. The quantized $x_q(n)$ sequence is then transmitted over the channel described in Fig. 6, detected using a self-coherent receiver and passed through the matched filter (MF), which outputs $y_q(n)$. Finally, the effective quantization at the receiver end (after MF) can be given as,

$$q_{eff}(n) = y_q(n) - y(n), \quad (8)$$

where $y(n)$ is the ideal received signal after MF (without quantization noise). The DRE method optimizes this $q_{eff}(n)$ noise seen at the receiver end. For the case of a linear channel, this can also be written as,

$$\begin{aligned} q_{eff}(n) &= y_q(n) - y(n) = x_q(n) * h(n) - x(n) * h(n) \\ &= q_{dq}(n) * h(n) = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} h(l)q(n-l) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $h(l)$ is the combined impulse response (CIR) of the channel and the MF, L is the length of CIR, and $*$ is the convolution operator [19]. The DRE utilizes the dynamic quantization approach where the quantized values $x_q(n)$ are chosen such that the resulting error sequence $q_{dq}(n)$ convoluted with channel impulse response and MF would lead to minimal mean squared quantization error (MSQE) as,

$$\text{MSQE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |q_{eff}(n)|^2, \quad (10)$$

where N is the number of samples in the input signal. To maintain consistency and easy follow-up, parameters and notations in the DRE are kept the same as discussed in [19].

B. Quantization Noise Analysis

The simulation results presented here correspond to the system model shown in Fig. 6. At the transmitter side, a

Fig. 8: Dynamic quantization noise analysis with different values L and M . Increased L improves the q_{dq} performance at an expense of high computational cost.

random bit sequence is mapped into an M -PCS signal and passed it through a root-raised cosine (RRC) filter with a roll-off factor of 0.2. The signal consists of 30 GBaud PCS-36QAM with a net bit-rate of 100 Gbps. Results shown in Fig. 7 present an analysis of the quantization noise with (w/) and without (w/o) DRE. Fig. 7a shows the magnitude spectrum for the rounding-off quantization noise $q_{ro}(n)$ (referred to as w/o DRE) for the CSPPR ranging from 3 to 18 dB. The x-axis represents the frequency in the GHz scale and the y-axis represents the CSPPR values. It shows that $q_{ro}(n)$ floor increases with increased CSPPR value. Also, it shows the presence of the harmonics due to the quantization of the virtual carrier with low PNOBs. Next, the magnitude spectrum data for the dynamic quantization noise $q_{dq}(n)$ is shown in Fig. 7b.

Fig. 9: Enhanced virtual carrier assisted self-coherent transceiver employing DRE.

 Fig. 10: Performance of DRE-enhanced self-coherent transceiver over 42 m FSO link for different PNOBs configurations. (a) NGMI vs CSRP, (b) SNR gain vs CSRP. (FEC limit @ $\text{NGMI}_{\text{th}} = 0.88$ with 20% overhead).

It shows that the implementation of the DRE reduces the in-band quantization noise (region A1 in Fig. 7b) and increases the out-of-band noise (region A2 & A3 in Fig. 7b). Further, Fig. 7c and Fig. 7d show the effective quantization noise $q_{\text{eff}}(n)$ at the receiver end (after MF) for the $q_{ro}(n)$ and $q_{dq}(n)$, respectively. Fig. 7c shows that the $q_{\text{eff}}(n)$ w/o DRE results in higher in-band quantization noise. The $q_{\text{eff}}(n)$ w/ DRE significantly reduces the in-band quantization noise as shown in Fig. 7d. Moreover, the DRE effectively nullifies the generated harmonics due to the RO quantization of the virtual carrier (see Fig. 8). Also, results shown in Fig. 8 show that the increased value of L shapes quantization better the expense of extra computation cost. Notice that, the increased value of L not only provides the in-band performance gain but also reduces the out-of-band peak as well.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the experimental setup used for the DRE-enhanced virtual carrier-assisted self-coherent transceiver, see Fig. 9, and obtained experimental results. At the transmitter side, a random bit sequence is generated and mapped into PCS-36QAM symbols. Notice that, the net bit-rate of the system is kept at either 80 or 100 Gbps (mentioned explicitly in the results), with a 20% forward error correction (FEC) overhead. The generated symbols are then passed through an RRC pulse shaping filter with a 0.2 roll-off.

Fig. 11: Obtained results for 30 GBaud PCS-36QAM system with a net 100 Gbps bit-rate w/ and w/o DRE.

Following that, a virtual carrier is added in the digital domain. The carrier power is kept sufficiently high to the minimum phase condition upon square-law detection and minimizes the impact of SSBN. The DRE method is then employed to perform the quantization noise shaping as mentioned earlier [19]. The DAC used for the experimental setup is powered by a Keysight M8194A arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) with an 8-bit vertical resolution, 120 GSa/s sampling rate, and an analog bandwidth of ~ 45 GHz. Notice that the PNOBs configurations can be changed by rounding-off operations in the digital domain before sending it to the DRE algorithm.

Fig. 12: Six hours long transmission over 42 m FSO link and performance assessment employing the mentioned experimental setup in Fig. 9, for 3, 4, and 5 PNOBs DAC configurations.

During the experimental analysis, we employed 3, 4, and 5 PNOBs DAC configurations considering both w/ and w/o DRE scenarios, for the performance assessment. The output of the DAC is amplified by an amplifier (SHF 807) and drives a single polarization IQ Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM). Subsequently, the modulated optical signal at the MZM output is passed through a waveshaper to remove out-of-band noise and then amplified by a booster amplifier before applying it to an optical collimator (F810APC-1550) for outdoor FSO transmission. At the receiver end, a beam of the optical signal is collected by the receiver collimator, located 42 meters from the transmitter. The received signal is then amplified by the optical amplifier and detected using a single photodetector. The output of the photodetector is captured by the Tektronix real-time oscilloscope (RTO) and processed offline.

The first step in the receiver DSP (RX-DSP) is estimating the carrier contributing factor (CCF). The CCF parameter is a key parameter of the DC-Value method since it enables optical field reconstruction by using the minimum phase condition. Unlike the KK method, the reconstruction of optical fields can be carried out by the DC-Value method at the Nyquist sampling rate [17]. Then, the data is passed to the DC remover and up/down-converted to get a signal in the baseband with a zero-intermediate frequency (IF). Subsequently, the least mean square (LMS) adaptive equalization with 51 taps is applied before the symbol detection. Finally, the system performance is assessed by evaluating the normalized GMI (NGMI) [23] between the transmitted and received (after DSP) signals.

A. Results and Discussion

Results shown in Fig. 10 present the obtained NGMI and corresponding SNR gain provided by DRE as a function of CSPR. Note that in the DRE algorithm, the memory order and the number of quantization possibilities are defined by L and M , respectively, as explained in section III. The performance evaluation considered DAC configurations with 3, 4, and 5 PNOBs. The results correspond to a 30 Gbaud PCS-36QAM signal supporting a net bit-rate of 80 Gbps with 20% overhead. Fig. 10a shows the relationship between NGMI and CSPR for DAC configurations with 3, 4, and 5 PNOBs. For the 3-PNOB DAC configuration, the results show that the 3-PNOB DAC cannot support error-free transmission without DRE.

Nevertheless, DRE can significantly improve performance and exceed the required threshold for error-free transmission by using FEC with a 20% overhead [6]. Using the DRE in a 3-PNOB DAC configuration yields a significant SNR gain of approximately ~ 3 dB (see Fig. 10b). Similarly, other results show gains of ~ 1 dB and ~ 0.5 dB for 4 and 5 PNOB DAC configurations, respectively. We also increased the net bit-rate to 100 Gbps with the same setup and configuration and obtained additional experimental results, see Fig. 11. In this case, only 3-PNOB DAC configurations with and without DRE were used. The results show that a DRE with $L = 3$ and $M = 3$ provides an optimal value of 0.83 NGMI. This is well away from the NGMI threshold required for error-free transmission. Additionally, increasing the memory ordering of the DRE method to $L = 5$ with $M = 3$ significantly improves performance. Results shown in Fig. 11 present the obtained NGMI as a function of CSPR for three different configurations: (i) w/o DRE, (ii) DRE with $L = 3$ and $M = 3$, and (iii) DRE with $L = 5$ and $M = 3$. For a DRE with $L = 5$ and $M = 3$, an optimal 0.9 NGMI is obtained, ensuring error-free transmission with a low-resolution DAC with PNOBs of only 3. Finally, we also perform long-term measurements to demonstrate the transmission reliability with such a low-resolution DAC.

Figure 12 shows the results obtained at a net bit-rate of 100 Gbps for about 6 hours (in clear weather), w/ and w/o DRE, in which the different measurements were taken in a time-interleaved fashion. From Fig. 12a, one observes that stable and error-free (NGMI above the 0.88 threshold) FSO transmission can be realized with 5 symbol memory depths ($L = 5$) and 3 quantization possibilities ($M = 3$). This is a reasonably low-complexity DRE suitable for practical implementations [19]. In Fig. 12b, it can be seen that error-free operation with 4-PNOBs DAC is not possible without digital resolution enhancement. However, a low-complexity DRE with $L = 3$ and $M = 3$ can safely bring the system into admissible operating condition. Finally, 5-PNOBs DAC configuration (see Fig. 12c) can support the transmission of a 100 Gbps system without employing DRE, but with a DRE, an SNR gain of approximately 0.8 dB can be achieved, which can absorb random SNR variations generated by atmospheric turbulence when the FSO link is exposed to more challenging channel conditions.

V. CONCLUSION

In order to tackle the cost and power consumption of high-capacity coherent FSO systems, we presented the first experimental demonstration of a virtual carrier-assisted self-coherent FSO link with a low-resolution DAC enhanced by the DRE method. The employment of the virtual carrier further simplifies the self-coherent transmitter architecture. Nevertheless, the insertion of the virtual carrier increases the dynamic range of the signal, which subsequently increases the quantization noise of limited-resolution DACs. By simulation analysis, we show that the signal clipping cannot help much to improve the performance, owing to the detrimental impact of clipping noise. Further, we applied dynamic quantization with the help of the DRE method to address the quantization noise issue. For 30 GBaud PCS-36QAM with a net 80 Gbps bit-rate transmission, the experimental results over 42 m FSO link show that the employment of DRE can provide significant ~ 3 dB, ~ 1 dB, and ~ 0.5 dB SNR improvement for the case of 3, 4, and 5 PNOBs DAC configurations, respectively. Also, a higher memory order in the DRE method allows to increase the transmission rate to 100 Gbps for the same 30 GBaud PCS-36QAM signal with 3 PNOBs DAC configuration. Overall, the employment of the DRE method enables self-coherent detection over a 42 m FSO link with a net 100 Gbps bit-rate using a low-resolution 3 PNOBs DAC.

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